

International Journal of Human Resource & Industrial Research (IJHRIR)

ISSN: 2349 –3593 (Online), ISSN: 2349 –4816 (Print)

Email: editor@arseam.com

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WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT: THE ROAD MAP TO INCLUSIVE GROWTH AND SUSTAINABLE GLOBALISATION

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Abstract

We always sermonise human rights, but often forget that women are human beings and like their male counterparts that they are the nucleus of our civilisation, they have been different roles to play in the ever-changing social set up. But even after 60 years of independence women continue to live in a state of neglect and exploitation. Mainstreaming of women into the new and emerging areas of growth and globalisation is imperative. Globalised capital has reduced everything to a commodity and everyone to a consumer. Nowhere is this more evident than in the lives of women. Women bodies are commoditised especially in sexual trafficking. Women constitute the greater proportion of exploited labourers. So empowerment of women is needed. The paper examines the role of women in socio-economic development and how their participation in economy help achieving inclusive growth and sustainable globalisation. The paper finds that women participation in decision-making or inclusive governance is indispensable for achieving inclusive growth. Therefore, the change in attitude towards women has necessarily to be driven by the political process. It is naive to expect genuinely inclusive governance without inclusive politics or empowerment of women hitherto not having access to political power at different levels. The paper concludes that here is need to strengthen and streamline the role of women in the development of various sectors by harnessing their power towards nation building and to attain inclusive growth and sustainable globalisation.

Keywords: *Inclusive Growth, Empowerment, Globalisation, Parliament, Decision-Making.*

PART I: AN OVERVIEW

INTRODUCTION

The concept of women has been best described in an ancient Sanskrit saying- “Yatra Nari Pujante Tatra Devo Ramante”. Women have been given the ascription of mother Goddess and are considered the source of *shakti*. According to Manusmriti, “Women must be honoured and adorned by their fathers, brothers, husbands and brother- in -laws who desire their own welfare, where women are honour, there the gods are pleased but where they are not honoured, no sacred rites yields rewards”(Giri Raj Shah, 1995:1). The role of women has to be visualised as described in the words of Tagore in Chitra: “I am no goddess to be worshipped nor yet the object of common pity to be brushed aside like a moth with indifference. “If you desire to keep me by your side in the path of danger and daring, allow

me to share the great duties of your life then you will know my true self”(Giri Raj Shah, 1995: v). God Shiva in his androgynous form as *Ardhnarishvara*, Shiva gets the credit for establishing gender equality. In his *sukshma* or core spiritual form, he established that *Brahama* created men and women as equal and that they represent, in turn, the powerful principle of creation as *purusha* and *shakti*. They are complementary and incomplete in themselves, if alone. The principle of the *linga* and the *yonis* or the union of the phallus and the vulva was to lead to creation. Women were to represent sexuality, sensuality and energy of creation while man, the *purusha*, represented power (Seth, 2001:12). However, women have been the subordinate gender in most of the history that we know, and they are still the second sex in all countries, without exception. The Report of the South Commission points that women account for more than half of the South’s population. They participate in the development process in a myriad ways, but their contribution to economic and social change continues to be inadequately recognised and greatly undervalued. They are almost invariably paid less than men for the same work and their entry into jobs are often blocked (Mehta, 1999). Male dominated cultures have given them an inferior position in society, and custom, taboo and the sexual division of labour keep them subordinate to men (The Report of the South Commission, 1990:128). There are different ways in which they have been subordinated by religion: whether it be *Hinduism*, *Islam* or *Christianity*. Within the *Christian* religion order the women are fighting to head the church hierarchy, the *Islamic* women cannot go to the mosques for ‘*Namaz*’ and the *Hindu* women cannot be *Hindu* priests also (Prasad, 1999:32-33). Religion – through Crusades and Reformation, destroyed most of the existing cultures and certainly constrained women’s freedom, incised into her liberties, degraded her rank and status and deprived her of the economic political activities through religious dictates and sanctions (Prasad, 1999: 33). Another ingenious movement relating to religion(s) may be seen as a mystical globalizing phenomenon that existed in the past and persist even today. The earlier religions may not have been lethal in their spread and remained only persuasive in proselyte (as some of the modern religions are so violent and cruel), yet their sway and homogenizing force did affect cultures and also the women’s position. There is no great world religion that treats women equally. Women have had less control over resources, (Bhattacharya, Malini, 2004: 03).

Globetrotting by the pre-historic man may be identified as one of the first attempts at ‘globalization’ howsoever limited, largely it was done for habitation in other parts of the globe that were found suitable for human and animal movement and transient living (Prasad, 1999:27). There is no evidence to show any sex discrimination at this stage. However, when men including women started organising into hordes, there began the development of culture of some sorts, struggle for existence, rugged living, crude fighting and fear and friendliness with nature. In the far distant ancient days, these hordes were led and dominated by women. It was in the migratory process of these hordes that women were divested of their leadership and control over the horde/clan tribe, and man made her subservient. Women’s child bearing speciality, physical necessity of confinement in pre-and post natal periods, intense emotional relationship between the women and her child, right to marry the daughter of one’s sister in the hand of maternal uncle, and patriarchy was cleverly exploited by the menfolk to subdue and relegate her to a subordinate position.

WOES OF WOMEN

Migration of human population, patriarchy and the rise of capitalism helped in the subjugation of women since early times. Globalisation instead of improving the situation has compounded it through its culture of consumerism. This culture has inflamed violence against women (Prasad, 1999). Patriarchy has completely influenced the authority pattern, property rights, inheritance, division of labour, pattern of behaviour and attitudes of the people most society’s world order. It has shaped the ownership pattern of property, pattern of political authority, roles of governance and nature of primitive and medieval political authority. It gave rise to feudalism treacherous global phenomenon.

It is an extraordinary thing what unnatural cruelties can be perpetrated all over the world under the crushing weight of long established custom and superstition. Open air and sunlight may not be denied to plants and animals if healthy growth is to be ensured and yet, under strict *Purdah* conditions, they are denied to women young and old all through their lives. They see no men except those of their own household, they go out veiled or in closed and curtained conveyances when they do go out at all, and even this degree of liberty is denied them under the strict *Purdah* condition (Eunice de Souza,2004:110).

Although women contribute generously to the world economy, their contributions are not counted on various grounds. While dependent housewives face deplorable conditions at home, working women are exposed to wage discrimination as well as to social, economic and sexual exploitation of varying kinds. Women's representation in various decision making bodies has always been lower than that of the men. Their representation in Indian Parliament and state legislatures has never crossed 7 per cent. (Verma, 2009:230). Women are just 18.4 per cent of the members of parliaments around the world. Many countries, particularly in the developing world, use quotas. Women member of parliaments have rarely come to the defence and support of women politicians when they are subjected to ridicule and humiliation on account of bias against women in politics. The absence of such gender-biased solidarity among women politicians is an important reason why they are being kept on the fringes of politics. Therefore, as a group, women remain weak and insignificant.

THE PSYCHO-SOCIAL DIMENSION

The status of women is more sociological in nature referring to a larger framework of society and economy, which is in keeping with the cultural history of women, differing from country to country and from time to time. We always sermonise human rights, but often forget that women are human beings and like their male counterparts that they are the nucleus of our civilisation, they have been different roles to play in the ever-changing social set up. But even after 60 years of independence women continue to live in a state of neglect and exploitation (Sreedevi, 2010:42). In discussion of women's status in any society, the general convention has been to assess their roles in relation to men. Two other dimensions in recent times have been introduced to facilitate such assessment, particularly in a period of change:

- The extent of actual control enjoyed by women over their own lives such as marriage, remarriage etc.
- The extent to which they have access to food, education and training, occupational advancement, migration, time and leisure, land and property ownership, life expectancy and decision making process.

The power of women on the other hand, lies more in the narrower context of individual limitations within the household. Thus, the two concepts can exist in a mutually exclusive manner. In economic terms, 'status' is a macro concept and 'power' is a micro concept. Status translated into the individual concept is power. '*Status*' refers to the overall position of women in society whereas '*power*' implies a woman's ability to influence and control at the interpersonal level. Power can be defined as "the ability to control or change the behaviour of others and the ability to realise one's will even against opposition" (Chatterji, 1993). In India, the status of women is vulnerable and miserable at various forms of gender disparities manifest in India. There are various dimensions of gender inequality viz; economic, social and political participation, opportunity, educational attainment, health and well being. Today, women are embracing the concept of empowerment because of their situations- their disempowerment and their unmet needs (Bakshi, 2002:1). Women's "empowerment"- that is learning through collective action that they can successfully challenge individuals and institutions to their self interests (Bakshi, 2002:12).

THE ROOTS OF EMPOWERMENT

The concept of women empowerment was introduced at the International Women's Conference held at Nairobi in 1985. The term empowerment is defined as, "a distribution of social power and control of resources in favour of women", (Dhanija, and Panda, 2006:12-15). Empowerment of women is the balanced distribution of power between both males and females. This powers can be the controlled over physical, natural, intellectual, financial and human resources along with the control over their self esteem. The concept of empowerment occurred primarily in developed countries, its roots are global. The roots of empowerment lie in the multifaceted efforts of many of those who experienced domination to achieve self-determination and to free themselves from external control- through revolution, other less violent forms of resistance, and nationalism. Both anti- colonialism and anti-dependency led to the evolution of empowerment theory and practice among women in the non industrialised world. Aspects of empowerment have been important in revolutionary situations in Latin America, Africa and Asia in movements for less radical social change throughout the Third World, in the civil rights and women's movement in the USA, and in the international women's movement today. What seems to be similar in these disparate settings is the opening of "social spaces' within which members of an oppressed group; can develop an independent sense of worth in contrast to their received definitions as second class or inferior citizens" (S. Evans, 1979:219). These spaces have led to opening of society. As Paulo Freire, one of the founders of the empowerment movement, said: "my experience in the sixties in the Brazil did not happen in the air. They happened in some historical, political, social, cultural elements in the atmosphere" (Bakshi, 2002:40).

The Oxford Dictionary (1994) defined "empowerment" as the process of 'bestowing power upon' or 'to invest someone legally or formally with power'. It can however, be contradicted as "true power cannot be bestowed. It comes from within (Rowlands, 1992:52). While Oxford Dictionary (2000) relates empowerment to authority, power, strength and confidence. The concept of women's empowerment comprises gender equality, status, and power. These three concepts together bring forth the concept empowerment. Empowerment implies exercising psychological control over personal affairs as well as exerting influence over the course of events in the socio-political arena (Gutierrez, 1990, 53-149; Parsons, 1991, 7-21). Empowerment is an active multidimensional process which enables women to realise their full identity and powers in all spheres of life. Empowerment is a process and includes the following components:

- Equal opportunities for using society's resources.
- Prohibition of gender discrimination in thought and practice.
- Special attention must be given to the needs and problems of women as one of the "weaker sections" of Indian society.
- Free from any insecurity, assault, violence or domestic violence, and having a choice in matters of reproduction.
- Freedom of thought and expression.
- Economic independence.
- Participation in all decision making bodies.
- Freedom of choice in matters relating to one's life.

INCLUSIVE GROWTH AND GLOBALISATION

With the growing globalisation and liberalisation of the economy as well as increased privatisation of services, women as a whole have been left behind and not been able to partake of the fruits of growth and globalisation. Mainstreaming of women into the new and emerging areas of growth and globalisation is imperative. Globalised capital has reduced everything to a commodity and everyone to a consumer. Nowhere is this more evident than in the lives of women. Women bodies are commoditised especially in sexual trafficking. Women constitute the greater proportion of exploited labourers. So empowerment is needed and steps taken by the government and policy makers (Sreedevi, 2010:42). Increased trade will have far reaching ramifications that will be especially critical for women in developing countries because they play a significant role in trade that is generally not recognised.

Expansion of trade may open up new income and employment opportunities for women. However, it may expose them to increased competition in global system. So as to ensure that this does not threaten their livelihoods, what is needed is support from government, non-government organisation etc. Trade had a major impact on the development of civil freedom or bourgeois freedom in Europe. It was seen as a liberating agency. More people could participate in it. In fact this is the central theme of our Eleventh Five Year Plan, where it emphasis on *"Towards Faster and More Inclusive Growth"*. The oxford dictionary defines inclusive growth as growth that "does not exclude any section of society or any party". It is a kin to the development strategies such as "growth with justice", "growth with equity", "growth with distribution", "growth with human face", "growth with distribution", "pro-poor growth", etc. suggested by many starting with Dadabhai Naoroji in the beginning of the 20th century.

The term inclusive growth is being discussed today not only in India but also across the world. Robert Zoellick, President of the World Bank Group, focused on the theme of "An Inclusive and Sustainable Globalisation", at a recent meet in Washington D. C. "Globalisation must not leave the bottom line behind remark the new chief of the World Bank. Inclusive growth is not only desirable from equity point of view but it is also important for ensuring stable growth. The inclusive growth can only be achieved by combining rapid growth with pro-women growth, equity and stability promoting growth. The strategy of inclusiveness required participation of vulnerable section of society i.e., women, children and poor people etc. Thus the strategy of inclusive growth is based on four attributes viz; opportunity, capability, access and security. Opportunity implies generation of more and varied way of livelihood for people to earn a living and increase their income over time. Capability implies that the economy is providing means for people to create or enhance their capabilities in order to exploit available opportunities. Access implies that the economy is providing means to bring the opportunities and capabilities together. Security implies the provision of means for people to protect themselves against a temporary or permanent loss of livelihood. These four attributes of inclusive growth must come at the disposal of the women. When this happened women will be empowered automatically and in repercussion lead to inclusive growth and sustainable globalisation.

PART II: THE ROAD TRAVELLED

In Vedic times the woman was an equal of man in all that matters. She chose her husband after she attained the age of discretion and understood her interests. There was no restriction on widow remarriage. This is accepted by scholars like Sir Herbert Risley^o. In certain respects the woman of Vedic times in India was freer than the European woman of even today.

In the real *Hindu* India of history, woman of any period enjoyed a better position in society than her European sister at any time before the mid-Victorian era (Shah, Giriraj, 1995:89). Before the advent of Islam in the early seventh century A. D. Women in Arabia enjoyed little respect. Their status was no better than chattels. In Islam, the honour and status due to women as human beings and members of the social community, was acknowledged and greater protection from the Sharia or Islamic Law.

The status of women was raised by Islam by granting her rights of property and share in her husband's or kinsmen's estate^o. The Prophet of Islam, who always adhered to the course of appeal and persuasion, counselled his followers that their wives and daughters should wear veils when they had compelling reasons to go out in public. The Muslims, all over the world, therefore, generally regarded women as creatures unfit for public duties. It is significant to note that the Prophet of Islam recommended "observation of privacy" for women, not their seclusion or confinement. Many Third World Countries today are undergoing what the Western media called "fundamentalism". Since the early seventies fundamentalism has been on the rise in the Islamic world and this has had repercussion in

several other countries including India. Subsequently, Hindu fundamentalism also reared its head and became quite aggressive (Shah, Giriraj, 1995:18).

In the Islamic world, the first victims of fundamentalism were women. Ideology of Islam began to assert that a woman's place was at home. Allah has created women to bear and rear the children and also to look after the comforts of their spouses when they returned home everyday. Hindu fundamentalists also want to curtail women's rights and deny them equal status with men. They justify *Sati* not only in theory but actively support it in practice. When *Sati* incident took place in Deorala in Rajasthan, even the Shankaracharyas came forward to defend it. What is more shocking is that communalists and fundamentalists mobilise themselves to strengthen conservative attitudes towards them. (Shah, Giriraj, 1995: 20). The BJP and other organisations in Gujarat brought women out in the street to fight their caste war in 1985. They came out in large numbers and fought with the police. One woman was made to rip her blouse on the road in order to accuse the police of molestation. When the caste riots turned into communal riots in Ahmedabad in March 1985, women of one community were instrumental in killing the women of another. Investigation revealed that a pregnant woman was thrown into a fire when the violence was at its climax by some men and women in her neighbourhood. Women should understand that men are using them for their own political ends. They should fight against communalism. If they win, the battle for women rights and equal status would be more than half won (Shah, Giriraj, 1995:21). The question of equal status for women was first raised in the early days of the founding of New England. Anne Hutchinson challenged the Puritan theocracy of Boston, in its assumption that no women should have a voice in church affairs

Ø Sir Herbert Risley was a pioneer in Indian Ethnography His chief book on this subject is "The People of India". He served as Census Commissioner to the Indian Government.

“The Koran, 4/8, “Men should have portion of what their parents and kindred leave, and women should have a portion of what their parents and kindred leave, whether it be little or much, a determined portion.

(Jain, 1978:213). Historically speaking the women's movement has been a middle-class one, attracting educated and relatively affluent individuals, and by and large, even today it has retained the same character. According to sociologist Joan D. Mandle, there are three broad groupings in today's movements. Firstly, there are women whose dissatisfaction focussed primarily on the ways in which society limits the personality development. This would mean the existence of opportunity for all individuals to choose their own goals develop skill and ability best suited to their natural talents. Secondly, there is the group of women to whom work and occupational discrimination based on sex stereotypes are of importance. These involve equal pay, security and an end of all forms of discrimination against women workers. The third group of women activists comprises those to whom the organisation of family life, child bearing and domestic care in American society is most salient. With both parents spending time at work and also at home, the false dichotomy between expressive and instrumental roles could be eliminated, as both mother and father could adopt identical roles. Thus crux of the feminist argument is that in a man's world, women still have a ritualised place "peculiar" to their sex. They are received warmly only in women centred trades like fashion or in acting. Women virtually have no access to power money and sex – the three great values which America has today. In some countries they do not have right to own land. They have less access than men to credit and limited access to such productive resources as irrigation, water, fertiliser, and technology. It is also evident that health services and educational facilities are not equally available to them. Feminists argue that women can get money but mostly through sex – either legitimate sex, in the form of marriage, or non-married sex. Sexual freedom is not enough. What lead to money and power is education and the ability to make money apart from sex. To put it simply, it is to achieving this goal that the women's lib movement and the "feminist cult" seem to be directed (Jain, 1978:248). Till the end of the nineteenth century, women in India were crushed under the weight of evil customs like infanticide, child marriage and *Sati*. They were

socially weak economically dependent and politically powerless. Though women have a large stake in politics, as large as that of men but very few Indian women really wield political power. History is resplendent with examples of powerful women rulers like Lakshmi Bai or Razia Sultan, and the glaring fact cannot be overlooked that women never wielded political power through recognised channels. Though some powerful women like Sarojini Naidu and Indira Gandhi achieved glory and fame in political life, yet the political arena largely remain a field unploughed by women (Desai and Maithreyi, 1987:293,294).

Annie Beasant, Margaret Cousins, Sarojini Naidu, Heerabai Tata and other educated women in women's organisations worked actively for generating political consciousness among women. A deputation of women met Montague in 1917 to demand right to vote for women. The province of Madras took lead in the matter and Dr. Muthulakshmi Reddi became the first woman legislator. Vijayalakshmi Pandit became the minister for local self-government in U.P. Some women like Sucheta Kripalani, Ammu Swaminathan and Sarojini Naidu contributed their politician acumen and experience as members of the constituent assembly (Desai, Neera and Krishnaraj, Maithreyi; 1987: 294).

The expansion of educational and employment rights for women that occurred during the early women's rights and suffrage movement failed to produce full and equal participation. In fact, by 1965, although large number of women were attending college or working outside of the home, they are still being discriminated in all spheres of life. The words of the first women's rights leaders had continuing validity: men still monopolized all profitable enjoyments, and women were permitted to follow; she receives scanty remuneration (Bakshi, 1998:39). The slow progress was partly due to the absence of the laws guaranteeing equal employment or educational rights for women during the two early women's movements.

In 1946, the U.N. established a commission on the status of women that lay dormant for almost thirty years, until the 1970s. The 1970s were a time of growing feminism, growing awareness of women's situation and increasing activism. In response, the U.N. reactivated the Commission and declared 1976 to 1985 to be the U.N. Decade for Women. They held the first International Women's Conference in Mexico in 1975, the second in Copenhagen in 1980. These conferences have defined women's concerns and confronted national and international powers with their issues. They have brought three sets of women contributors – advocates and practitioners, scholars, and grass roots activists – women are no longer invisible and no longer unheard. They have claimed their voices (Bakshi, 2002:12).

So far as women labour class are concerned, various schemes are designed to make their participation viz; STEP- Support to Training and Employment Programme for women, for rendering support to women's employment in various sectors such as khadi and village industries, agriculture, dairying, fisheries, handicraft and sericulture, handloom, and small animal husbandry, where women are predominantly engaged in work has been formulated during the current years. The Programme of Employment and Income Generating Production Units was started in 1982-83 for setting up projects aimed at income generation and employment on a sustained basis to needy women. This programme was implemented with the assistance of Norwegian Agency for International Development (NAID). Training was provided to develop their skill, leadership quality, and thereby to increase their employment rate and participation rate.

WOMEN EMPOWERMENT AND PLANNING ERA

All round development of women has been one of the focal points of economic planning in India. The planning process has evolved the years from purely 'welfare' oriented approach of women to currently their 'empowerment'. It was only from the Sixth Plan onwards that women secured a special niche and space in the national Plans and Planning Process. In the Sixth Plan (1980-85) we adopted a multidisciplinary approach, with special thrust on three core sectors i.e., health education and employment. In the First Five Year Plan (1951-56)

number of welfare programmes have been initiated i.e., establishment of the Central Social Welfare Board, Women Clubs, Community Development Programmes, and Organization of Mahila Mandals were a few steps in this direction. Women's education and measures to improve maternal and child health and nutrition services were received priority during Second Five Year Plan (1956-61). During this period, the empowerment of women was closely associated with the overall approach of intensive agricultural development programmes. In the Third Five Year Plan (1961-66) emphasis was on female education as a major welfare measures. Similarly, the Fourth Five Year Plan (1969-74) continued the emphasis on women's education. During Fifth Five Year Plan (1974-79), Women's Welfare and Development Bureau was set up under the Ministry of Social Welfare. For the first time, a shift was perceived from welfare to development approaches for women. This Plan coincided with International Women's decade and submission of report of Committee on the Status of Women in India. During Seventh Five Year Plan (1985-90), training and skill development were started to make women economically independent and self-reliant. This plan emphasised the need for gender equity and empowerment. A paradigm shift occurred in the Eighth Five Year Plan, where 'empowerment' of women was recognized and accepted as a distinct strategy. The Eighth Plan (1992-97) advocated equity and participation of women in the process of development. It focused on empowering women at grassroots level through Panchayati Raj Institutions. The Ninth Plan (1997-2002) took a major leap by incorporating 'empowerment of women' as one of the primary objectives of development. During this period the empowerment efforts have been geared towards women in the farming community because of their larger and growing presence in various activities of farming i.e., livestock, forestry, agro processing etc. In the Tenth Plan (2002-07) women's development was viewed as part of the development of the total community and therefore, was provided with adequate resources at all levels. This plan aims at empowering through translating the recently adopted 'National Policy for Empowerment of Women' (2001) into action and ensuring survival, protection and development of women and children through Right Based Approach (RBA). This Plan called for three pronged strategy of social empowerment, economic empowerment and providing gender justice to create an enabling environment of positive economic and social policies for women and eliminating all forms of discrimination against them.

The Tenth Five Year Plan categorised the development needs of the female population using the tool of age and classified them into five groups viz; the age group of 0-14, 15-19, 15-44, 15-59, and 60 plus and above. While age is an important marker in categorising women, it is also important to reflect on the reality that women are not a homogenous category. The draft Approach Paper to Eleventh Plan repeatedly emphasises the need to restructure growth as a brand and inclusive process. It frankly admits that even the achievement of reaching broad based and inclusive growth will not suffice to reach "certain marginalised groups". There are many groups of women who on account of tradition, culture, ethnic, social or religious background are more vulnerable compared to the women in the mainstream sector. These groups need to be specially focussed on in the Eleventh Plan. In the Eleventh Plan the focus should be on incorporating *gender budgeting* not only in traditional areas like health, education etc. But also in what is called "gender neutral" sectors like transport, power, telecommunication, defence etc.

The philosophy of empowerment for the Eleventh Plan is inclusive and integrated economic, social and political empowerment with gender justice. Though for the first time, a separate section on 'Gender Equity' was included in the Draft Approach Paper to the Eleventh Five Year Plan; the paper has not given enough focus on women's empowerment issues in the country. The strategy for women is confined to three areas – violence against women, economic empowerment and women's health. Over the years there have been efforts made to socially, economically and politically empower women but as a result of the lack of synergy or coordination between these activities, the outcomes could never be completely satisfactory. Unless the felt needs of women is incorporated and mainstreamed in the planning and development process it is apprehended that the fruits of economic growth are likely to completely bypass a significant section of the country's population which does not

augur well for the future growth of the economy. This called for a focused priority in the Eleventh Plan for empowerment of women in all its aspects. The mid- term Report also brought a number of focus areas which needed to be addressed of the objective of women empowerment is to become a reality. Some of the suggestions included a review of law affecting women and children, increasing women's participation in decision making. Specific suggestions were made of the need to strengthen the women's component plan as it was felt that there were a number of ministries and Departments, which had the potential to go beyond 30 per cent of funds under Women Commission Plan (WCP) programmes.

GOVERNMENT POLICIES AND PROGRAMMES

The preamble of the constitution speaks of equality of status and of opportunity. Equality of opportunity is a fundamental value in the modern world. Yet, as scholars examining the relationship between education and society have shown, equality of opportunity is not a cure for every form of inequality. Studies in the field of education challenge our commitment to equality in a fundamental way. How much equality should we strive for and at what price (Jensen, 1965; Beteille, 1983:3). Are there not inequalities in the natural distribution of talents that will come to the surface no matter what social arrangements we devise (Beteille, 1980; Beteille, 1983)? The Directive Principle of State Policy, embodying the major goals of a welfare state, also contains certain specific items affecting women. While the omnibus provision of Article 38 directs the State to bring about a transformation of socio-economic conditions for the common good. Another Article directs movement towards the achievement of an egalitarian and just social order which would affect men and women equally. Article 39 holds out the promise of an equal right to adequate "means of livelihood", "equal pay for equal work", protection of health and strength of workers – men, women and children – from abuse and entry into avocations unsuited to their age and strength (Mazumdar,1978:19).

The constitution of India not only grants equality to women, but also empowers the state to adopt measures to favour women and formulate women specific programmes and policies. The department of women and child development under Ministry of Human Resource is a nodal department, which formulates plans and policies, guides and coordinates the efforts of both government and N.G.Os working in this field. The government policies and programmes for women development began as early as 1954 in India but the actual participation began during Fifth Five Year Plan. At present, the Government of India has several schemes for women operated by different departments and ministries. Some of these are:

- National Commission for Women
- National Vocational Training Institute (NVTI), Noida
- Indira Mahila Yojana
- National Nutrition Policy
- Rastriya Mahila Kosh
- Balika Samridhi Yojana
- Rural Women's Development and Empowerment Project
- Women Labour Cell
- National Crèche Fund
- Women's Economic Programme (WEP)
- Swayamsidha
- National Social Assistance Programme
- Swa-Shakti Project
- Support to Training and Employment Programme for Women (STEP)
- Swalamban Programme
- Swadhar
- Employment-Cum -Income Generation-Cum Production Unit
- SBI's Shree Shakti Scheme
- National Perspective Plan for Women
- NGOs Credit Scheme

- Socio- Economic Programme (SEP)
- Women's Development Corporation Scheme
- Condensed Courses of Education and Vocational Training for Adult Women (CCE&VT)
- Mahila Samridhi Yojana (MSY)
- Training of Rural Youth and Self -Employment (TRYSEM)
- National Policy for Empowerment of Women 2001
- National Resource Centre for Women
- Integrated Rural Development Programme
- Prime Minister Rojgar Yojana
- Development of Rural Women and Children in the Rural Area (DWCRA)

PART III: THE ROAD AHEAD

In fact after independence, it was made obligatory to consider women as weaker sections of society and the constitution has guaranteed certain Fundamental Rights and special provisions for protection of women. Woman empowerment is fast emerging as an important slogan for the 1990s. This slogan is gradually being integrated with that of participation, advanced so vociferously by many in the late 1990s and 1980s participation as a key to development was found to be highly misleading because once concepts regarding women's work were redefined, the visible women of earlier times were suddenly perceived as 'working women' and thus already participating in their own way in development (Mittal, 1995: 107-108). In recent years, there has been an increasing awareness and recognition of the fact that woman who formed half of the society, cannot be ignored. Neglect of women in our society is perhaps the most important cause of our backwardness. Even more serious, the population belonging to socially and economically disadvantaged sections like scheduled castes, scheduled tribe, and backward classes, large majority of minorities, women and children have benefited least from high growth and rising prosperity (Rao,2009:9). The slow improvement in the various development indices for these sections and the slow rise in public expenditure targeted to them as well as for social sectors like health, education and poverty alleviation programmes, and greater vulnerability of the poor to various kinds of risks in this periods have been documented extensively in the literature (Radhakrishna and Ray, 2005; Government of India, 2006; Dev,2008, Kannan,2009).

Growth by itself, far from reducing the risk of poverty for the socially excluded groups has in fact increased such risk due to market failures arising from discrimination as well as public interventions that are both inadequate and discriminatory in operation. A two-pronged strategy to address the problem is called for: first,'social and economic empowerment' of the excluded groups by improving ownership of capital assets like land, business, education and skills, and second, providing equal opportunity to them through legal safeguards, reservations and similar measures in public as well as private sectors, and by ensuring adequate participation in governance at various levels (Rao, 2009:10). Achieving equity through such measures will not only restore self-esteem and confidence among the socio-economically disadvantaged section, but also improve the overall efficiency of the economic system and ensure the sustainability of growth momentum by tapping the vast underutilized human potential (Thorat and Newman, 2009).

Countries that hope to be in the vanguard of our economic development and social change should accord women as a high status as that of men to enable both the sexes to play the necessary complimentary role in the progress of the nation. No country has developed rapidly over a long period without having been to some extent liberating women from their traditional household chores and without their close association in various socio-economic productive oriented programmes. The planners and policy makers are also aware of the crucial role of the women in economic development and are making efforts to encourage greater participation of women through development of their entrepreneurship skill. Majority of women do not undertake entrepreneurial venture. Entrepreneurship is a key to economic development of a country. The Government of India notes women

entrepreneurship as “ an enterprise own and controlled by women serving a minimum financial interest of 51 per cent of the capital and giving at least 51 per cent of the employment generated in the enterprise to women”. Entrepreneurship of women will not only enable them to get better jobs and economically self-sufficient or independent, but socially will also gain. Movement of a woman a step ahead leads to the movement of family, society and ultimately whole nation. Employment gives economic status to women. Economic status paves the way for social status to women. Today, perhaps no field is inaccessible to trained and modern highly educated women. U. N. Commission on status of women says: “women constitute half of the world’s population, accomplish about two thirds of its work hours, receive one tenth of world’s income”

The problem of inclusive economic, social and political empowerment is very basic to the survival and growth of the weaker sections of society. The Reserve Bank used the term ‘financial inclusion’ for the first time in its Annual Policy Statement of 2005-06 to bring all section of societies in the process of inclusive growth (RBI, 2008-09). Following the introduction of economic reforms in the 1991, there was retrogression on several indices of financial inclusion reflecting a severe setback to the objectives with which major commercial banks were nationalised in the late 1960s (Rao, 2005; Shetty, 2009). This experienced has prompted renewed policy attention to the issue of financial inclusion in India in recent years (Government of India, 2007).

Financial inclusion could go a long way in women empowerment by extending subsidies to make up the losses on account of lower rates of interest charged to the weaker sections and rural and urban poor women. In practice, however, restriction or bank credit to such transaction cost or risks but by the financial sector reforms implemented in 1990s which have also resulted in the emergence of an inequitable interest rate structure. For instance, paradoxically, a small farmer was made to pay an interest rate of 12 per cent while a highly rated corporate entity could raise money from banks at 6 per cent (Mazumdar, 2009). Therefore, the basic cause for financial exclusion, often missed, is a mindset lacking in social concerns. It is important to mention here SEWA Bank, through its success, SEWA Bank proved that the poor were bankable and helped paved the way for the emergence of hundreds of MFIs during 1980s and 1990s.

Development efforts must touch all sections of the society. However, fruits of globalisation are being shared by the privileged classes across the globe. Unlike men women are not usually in concert with modern society. They are often hindered by modern society, and must wrest their power through concerted action, power has not trickled down to them, nor have they been absorbed into the process of development whereas man was modernised through his contact with modern institutions: formal schooling, factories, banking, and cities etc. Women are also sometimes both modernised and empowered in these settings, but women’s communal activities, which can lead to empowerment, often take place in the most traditional of settings or under the most deprived conditions. Women are often reacting to rather than flowing with the times (Bakshi, 2002:03)

Women empowerment and women education are correlated. Without education women are unable to access well- paid formal sector jobs and financial independence. Education is an asset, which can be realised in terms of entitlements. Education not only opens up vast avenues and opportunity for growth but affects families and future generation as well. Educating a girl child is one of the most effective means to have greater access to information and resources and to counter various forms of discrimination. Educational attainment is the most fundamental prerequisite for women empowerment. Education is a key intervention in initiating and sustaining processes of empowerment. Good quality education can help women and marginalized communities improve their status, especially in terms of the inclusion of marginalized sectors within governance processes. As our former President A.P.J. Abdul Kalam has pointed out that “empowering women is a perquisite for creating a good nation, when women are empowered, society with stability is assured.

Empowerment of women is essential as their thoughts and their value systems lead to the development of a good family, good society and ultimately a good nation”.

In the era of globalization, employment creation and raising employability has been a major challenge. The Eleventh Plan also states “generation of productive and gainful employment, with decent working conditions on a sufficient scale to absorb our growing labour force, from a critical element in the strategy for achieving inclusive growth”. As producers, women contribute to national product and welfare (whether measured or not) and generate income for the household. Women are proportionately most significant in the agricultural labour force, accounting for over 36 per cent in developing countries as a whole (Steward, 1992:24). In India, approximately 80 per cent of women workers work in agriculture, about 8 per cent in manufacturing and processing, over 7 per cent in services, 2 per cent in live stock, dairying, fishing etc; and less than 1 per cent in construction. About 70 per cent of women in Bangladesh, 95 per cent in Nepal, 36 per cent in Sri Lanka work in agriculture (World Bank, 1991:81). Their role is especially large in the informal sector, manufacturing sector viz; light industry such as textiles and clothing, food processing and in assembly line jobs such as semi conductors and consumer electronic goods (UNIDO, 1989:37). A large number of women are employed in production, processing and marketing of spices produced. Most of the spices produced come from the unorganised backyard farm sector, cultivated mainly by women.

Catalytic support is being provided in key areas to upgrade quality and promote export of value added spices. Trainers, exporters and farmers will be trained and gender sensitization will be emphasized in view of the important role of women in this sector. Groups of women will be used as ‘agents of change’ to educate spice growers about the need for quality. NGOs will facilitate linkages with on - going programmes like DCRA, ICDS, etc. In addition, well planned marketing missions to key markets will be organised (UNDP, 1992). Along similar lines, some of the corporate sector and other companies in the footwear sector are providing work to womenfolk in their houses. One project being implemented by Kasturba Gandhi National Memorial Trust – a voluntary organisation founded by Mahatma Gandhi – is training women in use of machinery, particularly sewing machines in making components of footwear. The objective is to empower rural womenfolk through training so that they can make up gainful work and earn an income (Mehta, 1999:73).

Development in international trade affects women both positively and negatively. Identification of sectors in which employment will be curtailed is crucial for the planned development of credit, training and skills to ensure that alternatives can be found. The need for such compensatory policies must be highlighted at all levels so as to mitigate adverse consequences for women and support their development (Mehta, 1999:74).

The Report of the World Commission on the social dimension of globalisation drew attention to the need to make decent and productive employment a central objective of macroeconomic and social policies as a key instrument to promote fairer globalization.

NATIONAL POLICIES FOR WOMEN

Although women now serve in combat or near combat roles in various armies, they are conspicuous by their absence from the peace making process – as from political decision making in general. The sole consolation, which carries some hope for the future is that war, and the immediate aftermath of war, can undoubtedly stir women’s awareness of the inequities under which they labour. Not surprisingly, many became active in peace movements. And no less surprisingly, an even larger number begin to campaign for their rights (Giri Raj, Shah; 23). The National Policy for Empowerment of Women 2001 has at its goal bringing about advancement, mainstreaming a gender perspective in the development process, elimination of discrimination at all levels equal access to women to health care, quality education, career and vocational guidance, employment, equal remuneration, occupational health and safety, social security and public office, participation and making of women in social political and economic life of the nation, development and empowerment of

women at all spheres of life through creation of a more responsive judicial and legal system sensitive to women and mainstreaming a gender perspective in the development process. The National Policy for Empowerment of Women in its goals and objectives states that the “de facto enjoyment of all human rights and fundamental freedom by women on equal basis with men in all spheres – political, economic, social, cultural and civil will lead to real empowerment of women.

The present Government in their National Common Minimum Programme have laid down six basic principles of governance one of which is to empower women politically, educationally, economically and legally. The National Policy for Empowerment provides for strengthening the existing mechanisms (viz; Government, non- government, central and state government, local government), which support the cause of women’s advancement through interventions as may be appropriate and will relate to, among others, provisions of adequate resources, training and advocacy skills to effectively influence macro-policies, legislation, programmes etc. To achieve the empowerment of women, the policy also provides for setting up of national and state councils to oversee the working of the policy on a regular basis and review the progress made in implementing the policy twice a year.

It has been increasingly recognised that centralized approach has not produced desired results, especially in terms of inclusion of marginalized groups, especially women. Through 73rd and 74th constitutional amendments and continued administrative decentralised through programmes like NRHM, have demonstrated the Government of India’s commitment to increasing the political participation of women. Besides, Millennium Development Goals have been promoting gender equality and empowerment of women and improving maternal health.

Market friendly policies generate high growth rates that failed to translate into improved standard of health, education and health security. Since increased women’s labour force participation and earning are associated with reduce poverty and faster growth, women will benefit from economic empowerment but so too will men, children and society as a whole. Thus, it is extremely important to ensure that women are economically empowered. There are various factors that contribute to the economic empowerment of women. These factors operate at various levels viz; macro-policy level, meso-community level and micro-household level. Women’s representation in better remuneration job at national and state level are part of macro-policy level while meso-community level comprises ownership of assets and land, access to credit and markets. Micro-household level include women’s control over income, relative contribution to family support, access to and control of family resources (Report of the Working Group,2006:22).

MICRO CREDIT AND WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

Micro credit is promoted as an entry point in the content of the wider strategy for women’s economy and socio-political empowerment that focuses on gender awareness. The origin of micro credit can be traced to the 1976 when Mohammed Yunus set up the Grameen Bank experiment on the outskirts of the Chittagong University Campuses as an experiment. Yunus is recognised as the father of micro credit, just as M. S. Swaminathan is considered as the father of the Indian Green Revolution. Both inventions have made a huge difference to the lives of the millions of people, particularly to the rural poor. Since the micro credit revolution came a whole decades or two after the green revolution, it was more sensitive to the issue of poverty and gender inequality and thus had in its design a focus on the poor, if not the poorest, and specifically on women (Ray, 2003; Hariharn; 2005). Micro credit is emerging as a powerful instrument for women empowerment in our economy. In India, micro credit is dominated by Self-Help Group Scheme (SHG) and Individual Banking Programmes (IBPs).

The SHG is the micro finance methodology in India. The operations of 15-25 members SHGs are based on the principle of revolving the members’ own saving. Micro-finance

Institutions (MFIs) and banks augment the resources of SHGs. Saving thus precede borrowing by members (Rajesh & Venkatamma, 2009). Rapid progress in SHGs formation has now turned into an empowerment movement among women across the country. The SHGs are strengthening collective self help capacities of the poor, especially women of the weaker sections at local level, leading to their empowerment.

Individual Banking Programme is increasingly popular for microfinance particularly through co-operatives. IBPs entail the provision by MFIs of financial services to individual clients – though they may sometimes be organised into joint liberty groups, credit and savings co-operatives or even SHGs. In 1974 SEWA Co-operative Bank was established to help low income women and reduce their dependence on money lenders. Much like Grameen Bank in Bangladesh, SEWA Bank relied on peer pressure groups to ensure high loan repayment rates. The training provided by Panchayat Level Development Planning (PLDP) unleashed the creativity that had remained dormant in women. Muslim women are also coming forward in organising and coordinating SHGs in the Panchayat. The muslim women SHG idea was mooted by minorities welfare department under the Development of Minority Women in Urban Area (DOMWUA), which is designed exclusively for muslim women living below poverty line.

GLOBALISATION AND WOMEN

The changing socio-economic scenario and the phasing out of the joint family system along with poor community based protection systems are some of the reasons why women are becoming increasingly prone to violence and abuse. The weak law enforcement and gender insensitivity of the various functionaries failed to check the growing violence against women. At the same time, globalisation and liberalisation of the economy as well as increased privatisation of the services, women as a whole have been left behind and not been able to partake of the fruits of success. Further, globalisation has dramatically changed the conditions under which the work for gender equality must be carried out, especially in high growth country like India. While globalisation has generated opportunities for local producers and entrepreneurs to reach international markets, it has at times intensified existing inequalities and insecurities for many poor women, who already represent two-thirds of the world's poorest people. Since the gains of globalisation and growth are often concentrated in the hands of those with higher education and those who own resources and have access to capital – poor women are usually the least able to seize the longer term opportunities offered (The Report of the Working Group, 2006:21). Globalisation and growth have failed to bring all sections of society on the path of development. Globalisation and growth alone are not enough to bring development. The need of the hour is sustainable globalisation and inclusive growth. Mainstreaming of the women into the new and emerging areas of growth is imperative. This will require training and skill upgradation in emerging trades, encouraging more women to take up vocational training and employment in the boom sectors. Out of 397 million workers in India, 123.9 million are women. Only 7 per cent of the India's labour force is in the organised sector, 93 per cent is in unorganised informal sector. Research indicates that economic participation of women – their presence in workforce in quantitative terms – is important not only for lowering the disproportionate level of poverty among women, but also as an important step towards raising household income, women empowerment, and encouraging sustainable globalisation and inclusive growth. The rationale for economically empowering women is compelling for both its own sake (intrinsic) and for other spillover benefits (instrumental). However, participation alone is not enough, quality of women's work is critical. A key challenge is to overcome a situation where women may gain employment with relative ease, but when their employment is either concentrated in poorly paid or unskilled job.

'Global', today does not merely mean 'worldwide' but it is associated with 'terrestrial globe', and 'celestial globe'. The motive of this twofold process of globalisation – terrestrial and celestial, as it is understood today, is to exploit all available resources on terrestrial and celestial globe. It is to control the world through 'star war' and consolidate earthly 'economic

expansion' with severe diplomatic heckling, violence and hegemony (Prasad, 1999). The term globalisation was first used by Theodore Levitt in an article he wrote in the Harvard Business Review (1983). He used it in a limited sense – as a synonym for standardisation of a brand for international markets (Pal, 2009: 236). Professor Amiya Bagchi states that globalisation is the opening of trade connections between different countries. But that is not a new phenomenon; India has had trade relations with all parts of the world as far back as historical records can ascertain (Banerjee, 2004). Another point that is often argued by many critics is that globalisation is nothing new - the world has been globalised from the time that there were international trade routes in ancient eras, and colonization and internationalization and other forms of inter-country relationships have existed for a very long time (Gupta, 2004:101). Without going into the entire history of globalisation since the sixteenth century, here it is important to distinguish the current phase of globalisation from its earlier phase. Free trade and free markets have become the mantra of the current devotees of globalisation (Bagchi, 2004:05). What is new in the current phase of globalisation is: global finance, global production, and globalisation of the service sector.

The first is of course global finance. There is tremendous and swift movement of finance from various clusters to other clusters. Another feature of current phase of globalisation is global production. The story of an American based Telecommunication Corporation, AT and T provides a casebook example. Initially all its manufacturing and production needs were met by small companies in Louisiana – one of the cheaper labour markets in America. In the 1980's they shifted their manufacturing units to Singapore because they found the level of technological know-how there adequate and the workers available at a cheaper rate. But by 1990's Singapore too had become expensive, so they move to Thailand, and one can be sure that in the next decade they will move somewhere else. Their production process is global and the mobility of finance makes it possible for them to seek out the best deal in the global market place. Another aspect that affects a country like India, is globalisation of the service sector. All of these new modes of financial interaction have created a situation where it is no longer possible, perhaps, to talk about and discuss the contemporary world in the traditional terms that we are used to. Today, we no longer have mobility of workers-physically they are no migrant but the services are globalised. All these components of economic globalisation are leading to greater rationalisation and robotisation affecting reduction in employment and destroying both local agriculture and industry and debilitate the social fabric of most underdeveloped societies. There are number of generic reasons, which give rise to the dismal picture of women in the society. Poverty is increasingly becoming feminised – mainly on account of the fact that with globalisation and liberalisation, a paradigm shift in the country's economy has taken place skewed towards technology dominated sectors, rendering traditional sectors like agriculture unviable and without any security cover. Unfortunately it is in these sectors that women predominately eke out a sustenance livelihood. The lack of alternate employment, skill, training, or credit facilities for women, who seek it, is another factor that keeps them in poverty. Sustained and rapid growth rates are the most effective route to do away with the poverty of women. However, the main challenge is to ensure that growth is pro-poor and pro-women. The main task that needs to be undertaken during the XIth Five Year Plan is to ensure that women are at the centre stage of all activities – economic, social, and political. There is greater need to empower women (as they constitute almost 50 percent of the total population of the world) to face the evil face of globalisation. It is empowerment of women only can make globalisation sustainable.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

While empowerment may be the answer to some problems, it cannot solve all problems and will per se create new ones. Younger and older women may be pitted against one another in a situation, where power has traditionally accompanied ageing. It is wrong to attribute the existing deficiencies in decision-making and tardiness in implementation to the prevailing democratic system as such. Rather, they can be traced to the way the function of our

democracy has been twisted and moulded by the pulls and pressures from the vested interests. Democracy and state power have to become instruments for social transformation. This requires broadening and deepening of our democracy by effectively extending it to the grassroots.

Experience has amply demonstrated that women participation in decision-making or inclusive governance is indispensable for achieving inclusive growth. Therefore, the change in attitude towards women has necessarily to be driven by the political process. It is naive to expect genuinely inclusive governance without inclusive politics or empowerment of women hitherto not having access to political power at different levels. Thanks to the 73rd and 74th amendments to the constitution, which have elected them at panchayat level. The establishment of the institution of Panchayat at village level (village council) provided opportunities to women to participate in social activities. Apart from this, 73rd and 74th amendments (1993) to the constitution was made to provide reservation of seats to the women in the local bodies of Panchayat and Municipalities to ensure their participation in decision making at local government. Women to the membership of co-operative societies also opened new vistas for their participation in economic endeavours, depending on the nature of their economic activities (Mittal, 1995:107). Recent decision of the central government to enhance reservation for women in local bodies to 50 per cent and the ongoing efforts to provide 33 per cent reservation for women in parliament and state level bodies, would go a long way towards inclusive growth and sustainable globalisation. However, increase in the number of women member of parliaments through reservations will not lead to their empowerment if they stay divided and if there is no organised constituency of women ready to defend women politicians against gender-biased, slander and humiliation. Women suffer a thousand forms of discrimination. Foeticide, infanticide, and dowry deaths constitute a triple whammy of murder. Girls that survived are discriminated against (compared with sons) in food, health, education and choice of livelihood. Adult women suffer physical abuse and rape. Female workers are paid less than males (Aiyar, 2010). What will it take to become an inclusive, just economically, socially and politically empowerment of women. Economically empowerment of women will be an equally strong foundation of building the intellectual and human capital of the nation (The Times of India, 2010). There is urgent need to develop intellectual and human capital in India in order to have sustainable globalisation. Delivering inclusive growth is possible through the growth of our people. We need to impart skills, training and education at all levels irrespective of gender to match the needs of India. It is education, which enable them to have greater access to information and resources and to challenge various forms of discrimination. It is however, important to recognise that while being literate or educated is necessary for empowerment of women it does not automatically ensure it. For that, we need an education of good quality and promote critical thinking. The problem lies in the attitude of society, not of legislators, who already constitute an enlightened upper crust. To transform society, we need social activists at the grassroots. Without social acceptance, rules and laws on gender equality are difficult to implement. We need administrators, police and judges who will implement existing laws on gender justice. Having more females in legislature will do a little to change the grassroots reality. There is comprehensive approach involving three principles stakeholders – the government, the educational institutions and the industry – to empower women. The remedy for empowerment of women lies in a strong will power and a gender just reform in the whole system. It requires involvement of every segment of society, women as well as men, government, laws, judiciary, political parties as well as social reforms, religious leaders, journalists and media.

In a society, that has practised structured social exclusion for thousands of years; the concept of justifiable rights has a strong moral basis. Lack of ability to participate implies lack of full membership within the system. The government takes important decisions not only on important national and international issues but also on matters, which affect women's lives directly like maternity, childcare, nutrition etc. There is need to strengthen and streamline the role of women in the development of various sectors by harnessing their power towards nation building and to attain inclusive growth and sustainable globalisation.

It is not possible to have competitive edge over other unless and until the role of women is empowered. However, equality of status, power and gender is given to women in the preamble of the constitution to empower them. However, this is not enough, this power has to be acquired and once acquired, it needs to be exercised, sustained and preserved. In other words, empowerment is a process of awareness and capacity building leading to greater participation, to greater decision-making power

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